

A socio-technical perception on the impact of project management software in logistics and distribution center: A case study in Saudi Arabia telecommunication company

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Abstract: This paper observed the use of project management software (PMS) as a planning and organizing tool in logistics and distribution center in a Saudi Arabian Telecommunication Company. PMS enable the company to mix and match resources for any given task done. Twenty-eight respondents from various ranks have been interviewed. This paper uses Echo Method where results showed the most critical use of a PMS was in its support for control and scheduling, and resource allocation. The purpose of Echo method led towards the calculation of an Interaction Effectiveness Ratio of 1.5, which implies that the PMS is not a panacea for project management woes. This further means that for every three benefits found in using PMS, there are two constraining examples found. The project management team resolved these constraining events with the use of spreadsheets (Excel) for data analysis and mobile phones for communications. This paper concludes that an organization who works with PMS needs to assess the features carefully and to simultaneously look at the use of spreadsheets as part of its project management tool.

JEL Classifications: O30, O32, O33

Keywords: Cultural value analysis, echo method, interview technique, logistic project management, project management software

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1. Introduction

The logistics and distribution functions in many organizations have become the prime vehicle of economic achievements. Quite often, a successful organization would have a very busy logistics and distribution center. However, in today's chaotic and dynamic world, changes are the new norm, forcing everyone to be agile. With this situation, the logistics project management team attains agility by espousing the philosophy of project management. Ayers (2010), in Supply Chain Project Management, presented a road-map on how project management could be utilized well in the supply chain management area. Given these multiple challenges, the logistics project management team need to develop multiple projects, and resources needed to be spread out towards multiple goals (Ayers, 2010).

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These projects could be managed using various methodologies such as Prince2 and ISO 12207. Within this project management methodology are the project management tools, such as Work Breakdown Structure, Program Evaluation and Review Techniques, Critical Path Method, Earned Value, and Gantt Charts. Many of these would require quantitative skills that would take some time to develop (Nafkha & Wiliński, 2016; Simmonds & Pence, 2017). Further, the need for accuracy in estimating the needed number of days and resources suggests the need for a project management software (PMS).

The increasing complexity of projects has led more companies to seek support from project management software (El-Zamzamy & Hegazy, 1998). Information technology (IT) is involved and plays a vital role in the project management field by introducing essential computer applications that provide project management teams with solutions to minimize effort and time for critical project activities such as planning, scheduling, monitoring, and controlling (Anbari et al., 2008). This situation had made project management software as synonymous with information technology and information systems. The advances in user-friendly computer software and enhanced graphical presentation systems have contributed to the removal of actual problems connected with formal scheduling processes.

The acquisitions of project management software have changed the way the project managers and logistics coordinators perform their tasks. With PMS, the project team members can concentrate on particular tasks related to the projects instead of spending on other management-support issues which the computer can execute more efficiently (Conlin & Retik, 1997).

There is a lack of project management software studies in general, especially those that shed light on the software's effectiveness in helping towards attaining goals and objectives, and the fit between the software and its users. This paper examines the fitness relation (strength or weakness) through multiple open-ended questions in interviews with users of project management software in the logistics and distribution center in a Saudi Arabian telecommunication company using the Echo Method. The interview questions are intended to determine the software users' perception of how the system helps them get their tasks done. Further, the paper aim to identify how much of the features are supportive of their functions, how many are a burden and what fixes were used to deal with the difficulties.

This paper is organized by presenting the literature review and followed by research method section. The analysis and results of study are then presented and discussed, together with highlighting the conclusions and recommendations.

2. Literature review

Organizations in various industries are increasingly utilizing project management methodology to organize their work. In recent years, more industrial, commercial, and governmental organizations have used project management to achieve their objectives. However, nowadays projects have become complicated. This complexity is due to the vast number of interrelated tasks, many resource constraints and a large number of people. Project management software (PMS) provides much-needed help as it offers a set of tools to help identify and monitor project activities (Cline et al., 2010).

Ayers (2010) discussed the use of project management approach in supply chain management functions. He identified steps of identifying problems, causes, and cost reductions. He also

recognized the use of a project charter before the initiation of the supply chain improvement tasks (Ayers, 2010).

The business brand ModalTrans views each customer contract as a logistics project management (Al-Haderi, 2013). ModalTrans discussed various steps needed to complete a booking towards its completion. These involve talking with multiple carriers, identifying packages, uploading numerous documents, identifying and managing costs, and dealing with various invoices.

While Ayers (2010) discusses the improvement of the supply chain, Al-Haderi (2013) talks about the day to day operation of the logistics system within the supply chain. The project management philosophy is being utilized both for improvement and for activities. In addition to this, Whitty (2011), in his dissertation, claimed that the “we are hardwired for project management as our behaviors and artifacts are encoded across our biology and culture” (Whitty, 2011). In effect, Whitty has claimed that project management is a natural approach to any undertaking. As we see right now, the project management approach has been made easier by project management software.

Further, the internet and local area networks have transformed the project management software concept from being a personal desktop application to being collaborative and corporate-wide. The capability to be executed through the system would support project managers situated in different locations. This network-oriented design would have the regular project management support functions, and also, will be providing the following: knowledge management functions, process management, and communication and collaboration support (Chen et al., 2006).

The use of project management software package makes the project planner’s tasks easier and faster, and hence with lot less effort as to when compared with manual techniques. Further, PMS enables project management staff to perform identifying alternative resource allocations and schedule changes (Page, 1989). Page (1989), from his reader survey among IIE (Institute of Industrial Engineers), indicated that 80% of the respondents used project management software. Of these members, they identified four significant benefits of using a PMS, namely: tracking a project, time analysis, cost analysis, and resource analysis. However, the responses are varying.

Moreover, both ease of use and project tracking were features have been identified as the most critical for industrial engineers (Herroelen, 2005). Document management is another advantage of PMS that enables their user to manage, share, and get easy access to different kinds of documents such as plans, manuals, contracts, and reports (Loesch & Theodori, 2005). PMS could provide an active learning component to the study of project management principles (Cline et al., 2010).

Some studies have identified planning as one of the critical success factors in a project (Belout & Gauvreau, 2004). This paper’s result was in agreement with the outcome of the Ogunlan and Toor study when they concluded that the critical success factors of projects are planning and control (Ogunlan & Toor, 2008). Further, from the research by Liberatore and Pollack-Johnson (2003), 240 respondents from the Project Management Institute emphasized the use of project management software. 95% of the respondents use PMS for planning while 80% of the respondents use it for control. Two words are begging some explanations: control and planning. “Control” includes the processes of checking project performance and making modifications to the project plan as needed. Planning would suggest two more words: planning-exclusively and planning-with-control. “Planning-exclusively” means that users use

the software only during the start of the project, while “planning-with-control” would apply it for control as well and use it in the project lifecycle continually (Liberatore & Pollack-Johnson, 2003).

Further, from a survey by Herroelen (2005), 95% of the individuals indicated PMS as their primary planning tool, dominating all the other options. However, these assertions deviated from the results of two European research results conducted by Balakrishnan (2009) and Roberts (1992). Their investigation revealed that instead of optimization, communication and representation are the primary purposes of PMS. Further, the studies reported that there is a limited knowledge about its use as a means to support the planning process (Herroelen, 2005; Kumar et al., 2017).

Earned value is one of the essential features of project management software. As the project progresses, and at any point in time, the logistics project management team can determine the percentage planned and scheduled, the portion attained and how much in monetary terms those percentage values equate (Raby, 2000). These calculations allow the project management team to, within a narrow range of values; identify in advance the funds needed to finish the job (Fleming & Koppleman, 1998).

One other feature of PMS is its capability to edit project content, as well as control the allocation of resources based on resource variances and limitations. Also, PMS can constrain the project network to a real calendar while maintaining unbiased statistical parameters as well as risk management and resource optimization. This approach of focusing on the resource availability led to the idea of Goldratt’s Critical Chain Methodology which requires the insertion of the protective buffering mechanism (Herroelen, 2005).

In addition to resources, it also provides a similar controlling capability on cost. A PMS’s cost management feature enables the users to compare operating results against standards, timely cost details, producing and marketing performance, and margins. It is noteworthy to mention that the PMS can group the margins into customer, item, product, specifications, and bottleneck operations. It can also provide decision support for project control and capital program management (Barkowski, 1999).

Intensive and effective communication is increasing regarding importance in today’s information age, and it is a central factor for integrating people and making decisions to create successful projects (Do et al., 2004; Niazi et al., 2016). Even communication and involvement with clients in different phases of the project shows great importance as one of the factors of success of a project (Ogunlan & Toor, 2008). PMS needs to be a server-based application that can help a group of people to communicate and manage tasks associated with a project (Cline et al., 2010).

In addition to the PMS’s wide-range of available features and communication capabilities, various authors have evaluated the quality of PMS based on two general criteria: general software capabilities and the variety of the generated resource-constrained project baseline schedules (Herroelen, 2005). Although there are many evaluation efforts for PMS packages in the literature, the initiatives were descriptive and mainly described the available packages and their features, survey-reported desired software features and reviews and comparisons of specific packages. However, there is a lack of indication in the literature on the following: the extent of usage, the manner of use and reason for selection (Liberatore & Pollack-Johnson, 2003). Many companies that are using PMS end up using a small percentage of the features that the software provides. Statistically, 80% of the respondents report using only 20% of the many properties of Microsoft project management software (Coulmas & Law, 2010).

One desirable feature of project management software is when the user can set activity priorities and then make several runs varying these priorities (Woodworth, 1989). A PMS package must be selected based on its applicability. By making a careful choice, the selection could be optimized, meaning the firm is maximizing the return from the PMS (Conlin & Retik, 1997). Functionality, ease of use, and flexibility are three features that are most often sought after by the PMS users (Anbari et al., 2008).

Damiani et al. (2014) in their research on a project management software package for engineering, procurement, and construction companies, listed the following beneficial features: collaboration, issue tracking, scheduling, resource management, document management, workflow management, reporting and analysis, budget management and invoicing (Damiani et al., 2014).

Aside from the features already mentioned, we note the following factors affecting the selection of a PMS: number of tasks; the size of firm; the number of years of PMS usage; and the extent of PMS usage. These factors seem to be in proportion to the level of sophistication of a PMS chosen, except for the number of years of PMS usage. There are cases when even the early users of PMS have chosen a sophisticated PMS package (Liberatore & Pollack-Johnson, 2003). It is essential to consider the organizational factors in which the PMS package, a form of an information systems, operates and what impact these organizationally related factors may impose on the utilization of the PMS package (Anbari et al., 2008).

Anbari et al. (2008) have proposed a recent model for the PMS Package user-perceived performance. This model looks at three dimensions, namely: software characteristics, user characteristics, and organizational and project characteristics. These dimensions would have the following variables: quality of software information, user-friendliness, and range of features (software characteristics); education level, exposure, and training (user characteristics); and size of the organization, scope of the project, and complexity of the project (organizational and project characteristics) (Anbari et al., 2008).

They found in their study that various characteristics have a positive and direct relation to PMS usage. These characteristics are as follows: the software's user-friendliness, the range of features, quality of software information, organization size, project budget size, project complexity, user exposure on software, and educational level of the user all have a positive, direct relation with PMS usage. The proposed model was found to explain 40.52% of the variation in PMS acceptance and use, in addition to providing some evidence of the positive relation between PMS usage, project's effectiveness, and project's overall success. Quality of software information appears to be the dominant factor influencing PMS usage from the system characteristics, while project complexity is the dominant reason from the organizational contextual factors. Surprisingly, project management exposure and training level were found to have no significant relationship with the use of the PMS package (Anbari et al., 2008).

Further research shows that various human factors such as project personnel competency, proficiency, and their ability to know how to solve the problems, in addition to the leadership capabilities of the project manager can significantly influence the project outcome. A look at the studies shows that, unlike the issue of web-based PMS, the question of human and organizational factors are evaluated singly, neglected, or even overlooked altogether (Nitithamyong & Skibniewski, 2010).

It is worthwhile to note that spreadsheets, primarily Microsoft Excel, are used together with Microsoft Project. Solver in Excel is used to perform optimization, and later on Excel exports

these results back to the PMS (Valenko & Uros, 2017). Further, no matter how the imperfections of a PMS, project staff seemed insistent in using a PMS. Perhaps, it might be because of the positive contribution of a PMS to the project performance (Pellerin et al., 2013). While Excel is often quoted as the de facto spreadsheet software, it is noteworthy to identify various other spreadsheet software such as Quattro-Pro, WPS Spreadsheets, OpenOffice Calc, Libre Calc, and Google Calc.

Restating the literature from a different perspective, it looks like the project management approach works well when aided by the spreadsheet approach. The project management approach would have all activities enumerated in a rigidly specified manner. The availability of the spreadsheet approach offers the project manager a broadsheet of electronic paper where one can freely write as one conceives.

3. Research method

3.1. Study background

This paper observed the use of project management software by the employees of the logistics and distribution center in a Saudi Arabian telecommunication company. The logistics and distribution center serves the company's entire operational group with the needed logistics services. The company uses a functional organizational structure in which employees are grouped into departments based on their similar sets of specialized tasks (e.g., Sales, Marketing, and Production, among others).

3.2. Participants

One-on-one interviews, each lasting for approximately 30 minutes, were performed. The respondents interviewed belong to a variety of functional areas within the logistics and distribution center and in different hierarchical levels. The interviews were tape-recorded and subsequently transcribed. These transcripts of audio recordings became the basis for final data analysis. The respondents consist of three directors, fifteen managers, and ten supervisory-level employees as described in Table 1.

TABLE 1. RESPONDENTS INTERVIEWED AND THEIR RANKS

RANK	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Supervisors	10	35.7%
Managers	15	53.6%
Directors	3	10.7%
Total number of respondents (N)	28	100%

Source: Authors' analysis.

3.3. Interview approach: echo method

This paper utilizes the Echo method, which is a well-known research method in social sciences and studies that concern the social interactions of an organization. It is particularly useful to determine the characteristics of those interactions and the effects they have on the

work dynamics in the organization. It can be a supporting approach or even a replacement for survey-based social analysis approaches (Poile, 2008). The Echo Method approach connects directly to the work of Alex Bavelas in the early 1940s (Bavelas, 1942). The Echo studies undertaken from 1966 to 1969 were concerned with understanding how people in different cultures acted and behaved. The need for more practical research that is more sensitive and explanatory for interpersonal and social issues than the conventional quantitative research methods has encouraged and attracted those who contributed to the Echo approach's development to exert more effort in this tool of social research. This approach has led to a more insightful understanding of many organizational and social issues (Cunningham, 2001; Fernández-Alemán et al., 2016).

The Echo method enables a detailed analysis of task-related social interactions and the measurement of the degree of coordination within each link in a network. Socio-technical congruence is a term connected to the extent of the fit between an organization's social structure and the structure of the system it develops. It is essential to identify the communication lines within organizations, the impact of these communications on the project progress, and the meaning of this communication to each function unit to be able to measure the socio-technical fit (Raby, 2000). Respondents are describing their views and behaviors during a series of interviews as a reflection of their role, granting them an opportunity to reveal their particular viewpoint along with insight on their work positions employing their terminologies and jargons. This interview (Echo) method extracts context-specific information about the respondents' task situation as they see it. Furthermore, it captures real-task conditions with a minimum amount of researcher intervention.

The Echo method is an open-ended, semi-structured interview method conducted face-to-face with four parts. Part one of the interview's purpose is to get background information on the subject, such as their current role, amount of experience they have in this role, and the total involvement in logistics and distribution center. Part two's intent is to define essential communication modes. Participants are repeatedly asked to name any group or technology with which they interact to accomplish their tasks that result in an overall picture of the participant's immediate task-related social network.

After all task-related social network are defined, participants are asked to describe how other nodes affect their tasks in "helpful" ways (referred here as positive events) and "not so helpful" ways (designated here as negative events); how the participant handles each type of negative behavior (identified here as coping mechanisms). Specifically, participants are asked the following questions: "In the process of managing your task, what does Node A do that is helpful in accomplishing your task? Please give me as many examples as you can." A different question is asked: "In the process of managing your task, what does Node A do that is not so helpful in accomplishing your task? Please give me as many examples as you can." Finally, participants are asked: "What do you do when this not so helpful behavior happens?" The corrective actions available at the recipient node are used to indicate the coping mechanisms.

The respondents have been asked to provide concrete examples for each category (positive, negative and coping mechanisms). Getting specific and practical examples from respondents has the advantage of enhancing and encouraging them to provide descriptive information about the experience on the job. The utilization of specific examples when answering questions in the Echo method approach builds on an essential principle for its explanatory power, namely, "subjective probability," which indicates that people easily recall the most recent events and the events that have an impact on their lives. Examples of these

characteristics (e.g., current and with high impact) are the ones that we are looking for to produce a detailed and more accurate understanding of a phenomenon.

The collected data for positive events, negative events, and coping mechanism events from the 28 respondents will be carefully classified based on similarities into themes. The resultant sub-categories will be titled based on the standard theme they share.

4. Results and analysis

From the recorded interview responses, the transcripts were written up. From the transcriptions, we encode the interview responses systematically segmented into three categories: Positive Events, Negative Events, and Coping Mechanisms. These three categories paved the way for the analysis and derivation of meaning from the data. Table 2 shows the count of clear examples categorized into each segment and a concretely stated typical example.

TABLE 2. FREQUENCIES OF EXAMPLES PER QUALITATIVE CATEGORIES

CATEGORY	NUMBER OF EXAMPLES	TYPICAL EXAMPLE
Positive events	201	For example, able to quickly obtain the logistics contract versus the actual deliveries done.
Negative events	134	For example, requires some software knowledge in transferring project management software data into MS Excel.
Coping mechanisms	131	For example, MS Excel provided a lot of support for report formatting and variable calculations.
Total	466	

Source: Authors' analysis.

4.1. Overall interaction effectiveness average ratio

The overall organizational interaction effectiveness ratio is used to quantify the logistics and distribution center's (LDC) perception of the use of project management software. The rate of Positive Events to Negative Events, calculated from Table 2, gives the value of $201/134 = 1.5$. This ratio, called Interaction Effectiveness (IE) average ratio, tells us that for every one adverse event, there are 1.5 positive events mentioned by the whole sample interviewed at the LDC's in a Saudi Arabian Telecommunication Company. This ratio indicates that the use of project management software package does not solve all problems of project-oriented management at the LDC. It, however, provides hope that the software has more positive effects than negative.

4.2. Data categorization

As part of the analysis, we conducted several iterations of reviews of the responses for eventual placement into one of the three categories in Table 2 above. After categorizing the events into one of the groups, once more, these responses are reviewed for eventual

placement into a sub-category; here we refer to as a common theme. We labeled these with an appropriate name. The authors tried to minimize scattered data analysis by combining those groups containing very few cases (less than five) into one of the major groups that can overlap with the theme of the minor group to ensure a more meaningful and focused analysis of the results. Table 3 below shows the result of the sub-categorizing process into topics including the theme's labels, the description of common theme, and a specific illustration (typical example) of each topic.

TABLE 3. THEMES (OR SUBCATEGORIES) FOR EACH QUALITATIVE CATEGORY AND RELATED CONTENT PROPERTIES

THEMES	DESCRIPTION OF COMMON THEME	SPECIFIC ILLUSTRATION
<i>POSITIVE EVENT CATEGORY</i>		
1). Control	It is the constant and periodic process of checking reports and situations, to compare this to standards, and if necessary, to recommend the taking of corrective action through minimized deviations.	It is used in monitoring daily, weekly, monthly transshipment of goods.
2). Scheduling and resource allocation	Identifying tasks' interdependencies and sequencing and then assign for them the scarce resources (people, time, materials), available to accomplish the specific task, assignment, or project that meets the stakeholder's expectation.	It is used in allocating warehouse staff for each task per contract.
3). Ease of use	Efficiently enter all of your vital information, easily maintain that data as your business changes, quickly extract the crucial information in a usable format, produce a complete plan that meets your business's unique requirements and is user-friendly.	It makes performing tasks faster and requires less effort
4). Reliability	The software component will always produce correct and precise output, the software or any of its parts will not wear out, and the software can continue to operate under contingencies. It is the assurance that the software will function successfully within a specific period and conditions when used for the intended purpose and methods. The ability of the software to facilitate the user overcoming business challenges by providing the necessary data processing functions as needed.	It can calculate the time difference between time zones accurately.
5). Flexibility	The ease with which a system adjusts to changing circumstances and demands. The ease of adapting software to new requirements. The ability to modify e-business processes to customer preferences.	It can create logistics staff lists to search for documents export to Excel.
6). Decision making	The capacity of the software to support in solving some semi-structured decisions using some mathematical techniques and reporting the results as a periodic or special report. The process of ranking, sorting or selecting from various alternatives, and suggesting to users a specific course of action.	It is used in supporting my daily tasks based on information extracted from the system.
7). Communication and collaboration	The capacity of the software to enable users located in different places to work on a task or project simultaneously. The users can do the following: emails, online group discussions, instant messaging, group discussion, and alert messages. Further, the users can exchange, process and manage files, documents and other files of various types (video, pictures, sound, etc.).	It is multi-user software where managers of two or more distribution centers can simultaneously work on the Work Breakdown Structure.

TABLE 3. THEMES (OR SUBCATEGORIES) FOR EACH QUALITATIVE CATEGORY AND RELATED CONTENT PROPERTIES

THEMES	DESCRIPTION OF COMMON THEME	SPECIFIC ILLUSTRATION
<i>NEGATIVE EVENTS CATEGORY</i>		
1). Lack of control	The software is not able to simultaneously position side by side the planned accomplishment versus actual accomplishments. This weakness in the software will make it incapable of monitoring deviation from standards, and hence unable to provide corrective actions.	It is unable to visually show the reported delay in the delivery of shipments.
2). Poor scheduling & resource allocation	Not a useful tool for identifying tasks, interdependencies, or sequencing and then assigning for them the scarce resources (people, time, materials) available to accomplish the specific task, assignment, or project that meets the stakeholder's expectation.	Resource costs are not reasonable.
3). Lack of ease of use	The system will not assist you to enter all your vital information efficiently, easily maintain that data as your business changes, quickly extract the essential information in a usable format, produce a complete plan that meets your business's unique requirements, or be user-friendly.	Difficult to begin without having the right knowledge.
4). Unreliability	The software component will not always produce a correct or a precise output, the software or any of its parts could wear out, and the software may not continue to operate under contingencies. It is probable that the software will face failure for a specific period and under specified conditions when it is used in the manner and for the purpose intended. The inability for the software to facilitate the user to overcome business challenges by providing the necessary and accurate data as needed.	The PMS does not make a clear distinction between the planning phase and post-planning phase.
5). Not flexible	The existence of difficulties that make a system incapable of adjusting to changing circumstances and demands. The problem of adapting software to new requirements. The inability to modify e-business processes to customer preferences.	You can't work around the features and modify reports.
6). Weak decision making	The system is not facilitating solving business issues or generating precise, concise, and logical information as charts or periodic reports, or conducting mathematical simulations and forecasting that support the analysis involved in decision-making processes. It is not helping the users or organizations with their decision-making processes, typically need ranking, sorting, or choosing from among alternatives or directing them to a specific course of action.	The system does not alert the salesmen about destinations subjected to delivery charges. We don't deliver to all places free of charge.
<i>COPING MECHANISM CATEGORY</i>		
1). Seeking help	Reaching out to a friend, colleague, or expert; attending professional training or watching an online tutorial from which we can get assistance to get clarification on ambiguous, unknown, or new concepts.	I am using online help centers and forums specializing in this software.
2). Using other tools	The act of utilizing alternative systems in parallel with the existing one to bridge a gap in the capability of the functions characterized by the available network. The sought system could be either a low- or high-tech tool.	I am using Excel to generate Earned Value reporting.
3). Workaround	To handle or control a contingency situation, obstacle, or deficiency of functions while dealing with information systems to overcome them.	I am using Excel to get data from the PMS in a faster way.
4). Rechecking and redoing	To review results obtained from the information system used within or outside the existing information system to confirm the accuracy and rationality of the system outcomes.	You need to check your output against earlier forecasts.

TABLE 3. THEMES (OR SUBCATEGORIES) FOR EACH QUALITATIVE CATEGORY AND RELATED CONTENT PROPERTIES

THEMES	DESCRIPTION OF COMMON THEME	SPECIFIC ILLUSTRATION
5). Tolerance	The description of the passive action taken by the information system user when he/she is used to the deficiency that exists in the information systems and is not practicing any workaround techniques to overcome obstacles or annoying issues with the information systems.	There is no solution; they must do it anyway depending on the client's requirements.

Source: Authors' classification.

We had seven themes on the positive element side and six themes on the negative element side. The above categorization process revealed that most categories in the positive elements are symmetrical with those determined in the negative categories, except for the communication and collaboration groups. For example, we have “Control” and “Lack of Control,” “Reliability” and “Unreliability,” and “Flexibility” and “Not Flexible”. It is worth noting that the proposed subcategories or themes are not mutually exclusive, resulting in placing an example in multiple themes.

4.3. Categorical analysis of positive event categories

The theme “Control” contains the most substantial number of positive events examples, representing 30.3% of all the positive event cases obtained from the interviews conducted, followed by scheduling and resource allocation (almost 25%). On the other hand, Decision Making received the fewest cases with only 5%, followed by Communication and Collaboration with 9% of the cases. Table 4 presents the distribution of all positive event cases as perceived by all interviewed respondents.

TABLE 4. DISTRIBUTION OF POSITIVE EVENT CATEGORIES (201 EXAMPLES)

POSITIVE EVENT CATEGORIES	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY
Control	30.3%	61
Scheduling & resource allocation	24.9%	50
Reliability	2.0%	4
Ease of use	14.9%	30
Decision making	5.0%	10
Flexibility	13.9%	28
Collaboration & communication	9.0%	18
Total	100%	201

Source: Authors' analysis.

4.4. Categorical analysis of negative event categories

The highest proportion of negative event categories falls into the category of “Unreliability” of the project management software (68.14%). Lack of Control, Weak Decision Making and Weak Scheduling and Resource Allocation categories received the lowest proportion of

examples with 3.7%, 5.2%, and 7.5% respectively. Table 5 presents the distribution of all constraining elements examples as perceived by all interviewed respondents.

TABLE 5. DISTRIBUTION OF NEGATIVE EVENT CATEGORIES (134 EXAMPLES)

NEGATIVE EVENT CATEGORIES	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY
Lack of control	3.7 %	5
Poor scheduling & resource allocation	7.5%	10
Unreliability	43.3%	58
Lack of ease of use	25.4%	34
Weak decision making	5.2%	7
Lack of flexibility	14.9%	20
Total	100%	134

Source: Authors' analysis.

4.5. Categorical analysis of coping mechanism categories

After being asked, each respondent expressed how they handle the negative events categories. As a proportion of total Coping Mechanism category examples, Using Other Tools received by far the highest (41%), followed by Seeking Help (21.5%). On the other hand, the lowest proportions, 4%, and 14.5%, of coping mechanisms examples fall into the categories of Rechecking and Redoing and Tolerance, respectively. Table 6 presents the distribution of all Coping Mechanism examples as perceived by all interviewed respondents.

TABLE 6. DISTRIBUTION OF COPING MECHANISM CATEGORIES (131 EXAMPLES)

COPING MECHANISM CATEGORIES	PERCENTAGE (%)	FREQUENCY
Tolerance	14.5%	19
Workaround	19%	25
Using other tools	41%	54
Seeking help	21.5%	28
Rechecking and redoing	4%	5
Total	100%	131

Source: Authors' analysis.

4.6. Coping mechanisms used for a particular negative event category

The figure shows the pairings of the coping mechanisms to those of the negative events as experienced by the respondents. We are trying to observe if there is any pattern in the individual behaviors for specific techniques of coping mechanisms.

TABLE 7. MATCHING THE NEGATIVE EVENT CATEGORIES AND ITS COPING MECHANISMS CATEGORIES

PERCENTAGES (%)	COPING MECHANISMS	NEGATIVE EVENT CATEGORIES					
		Lack of control	Lack of scheduling and resource allocation	Lack of reliability	Lack of ease of use	Weak decision making	Lack of flexibility
14.50	Tolerance	0	10	15	18	0	19
19.00	Workaround	33	20	21	18	0	19
41.00	Other tools	67	60	42	24	57	50
21.50	Seeking help	0	0	19	40	14	12
4.00	Rechecking/redo	0	10	3	0	29	0
100		100	100	100	100	100	100

Source: Authors' analysis.

In Table 7 above, we show the negative events on the column headers, while the row headers would show the coping mechanisms. By scanning and analyzing the table, it is revealing that the use of other tools (41%) emerges as the principal coping mechanisms.

5. Discussion

As shown in the analysis, 30.3% of the responses identified the project management software (PMS) as a control tool. This paper's result which focused in logistic and distribution center (LDC) in a Saudi Arabian Telecommunication Company is deviated from Herrolen's (2005) study, which mentioned that planning and resource allocation is the dominant purposes for using PMS. Herrolen suggested that 95% of the PMS users consider planning to be the most dominant important factor for them. But our results agree with Pages' survey for IIE members in 1998, which concluded that tracking is the most important capability of PMS. Pages' study also showed that time analysis, cost analysis, and resource analysis are following tracking as the most critical capabilities of PMS, and all of them are somewhat overlapping between control and scheduling and resource allocation.

As a result, what Page (1989) concluded in his survey is in no small extent congruent with the results we obtained regarding the most perceived benefits of PMS in our study. But paying such attention for control may reflect the overall organizational tension and the tendency of managers and other employees to exert pressure on their subordinates to push them to fulfill their tasks in a manner that enables the organization to achieve its objectives. It is interesting to mention that Ogunlan & Toor (2008) had indicated that planning and control are major critical success factors of a project. Libratoro & Pollack-Johnson (1998) had mentioned that 95% and 80% of the PMS users are using them for planning and control, respectively. Consequently, our study outcome regarding the principal uses of PMS capabilities aligns with what previous researchers found in their studies. But no one mentioned in the literature the negative consequences of using PMS as an extensive control tool.

When we discussed about control, we need always to consider that in theory there is an ideal balance possible between control and risk (Butterfield & Thomasen, 1993). Directing a lot of limited resources (mostly individuals' available time) toward excessive control could lead to the increase of the overhead cost and creating a bureaucracy that hinders the agility of the organization and its adaptability for the dynamic changes that characterize the projects' business environment in general. This behavior will result in raising the overall cost of the

project and compromising the profitability and the feasibility of the projects. Although there is a positive correlation between control and quality that results in cost reduction, this positive relation will break even at some point to cause a gradual increase in the overall project cost. Furthermore, excessive control can adversely impact the organization's creativity, and using control systems such as the interactive use of a management control system can negatively affect the creative performances of highly innovative firms (Bisbe & Otley, 2004; Conforto et al., 2014).

Also, in the positive-effect categories, we found that 2% of the examples mentioned reliability. We should not be surprised by this number simply because PMS users consider reliability as default and primary advantage for using PMS in the first place.

Collaboration and communication features did not gain a lot of the proportion of the positive element examples (9%), and perhaps the pervasiveness of high communication tools and software (available in smartphones) has caused the importance of this capability in the PMS to diminish compared to other abilities. In other words, PMS users have other options for effective communication and collaboration outside the PMS environment (Kumar et al., 2017).

On the other hand, the unreliability of PMS (43.3%) was the largest in the negative event categories, which is more or less almost half of the examples mentioned by the respondents. Further, it is also noteworthy that the reliability theme is merely 2%. It is important to recall that, in the subjective probability concept – a basis of Echo method, respondents will remember events that are either recent or had a severe impact. PMS end-users assume reliability in the positive events cases as givens, and will merely praise its inclusion, but when it is non-existent, the expected complaint rate is much higher (Conforto et al., 2014).

Some research papers have mentioned the unreliability of PMS such as Woodwoorth (1989), Reyck (2010), El-Zamzamy & Hegazy (1998) and Ngassam et al. (2008). They suggested that optimized utilization of limited resources is not perceived. This observation might be due to reported lack of accuracy, inconsistency, and non-logical forecasting. The reliability of PMS is an issue that could affect the level of use of existing PMS users. The technical readiness (TR) theory indicates that individual online behavior is being influenced by how the user perceives the quality of the information system supporting their work. Also, Anbari et al. (2008) emphasized the positive correlation between usage and level of satisfaction for the PMS. Furthermore, Kuo (2009) stressed the importance of users' perception of processing integrity and system reliability. Hence, PMS reliability is the backbone for any future improvement projects by the technology suppliers.

Moreover, "Using Other Tools" as a coping mechanism is the biggest regarding percentage. It is almost half of the entire coping mechanism category. By "Using Other Tools," we mean any method or alternative tool a PMS user opts to use to facilitate a function that the PMS package cannot fulfill, regardless of whether the selected process is sophisticated or not. Many of the examples under this category indicated that Excel is bridging a lot of the deficiency gaps in the functioning capacity of the PMS. One reason for this is that the PMS package selected does not fit entirely well the requirements of the organization. There seems to be a lack of employees' involvement in the PMS selection decision to determine what they need from the system (Simmonds & Pence, 2017). Also, there is an absence of consideration of factors such as organization size, project complexity, industry type, organizational context, and project nature (clear vs. ambiguous) when selecting PMS. When an organization buys the wrong PMS that neither matches its characteristics nor its project nature, parallel systems will be needed to fill the gap (Damiani et al., 2014).

Rechecking and redoing was least observed, in only 3% of the examples. One explanation for that could be the nature of this action, which breaks from the use of sophisticated systems (Niazi et al., 2016). Table 7 shows the result of further analyses conducted for the coping mechanisms' solution for each adverse event. In the table, "Using Other Tools" is the most frequently used option for the respondents who encounter negative situations while using PMS. The only exception was in the theme "Lack of Flexibility," which tends for PMS users to "Seek Help." We note that this result is a very valid observation since this "Lack of Flexibility" theme would have the following attributes: difficulty, unfamiliarity, and ambiguity. So, the most probable action would be to look for assistance as a way to reduce those attributions. The help and support offered by an individual could be a lecture, tutorial, and online forum discussions (Do et al., 2004).

Many factors contribute to the effectiveness of using PMS. Some of these factors are organization characteristics; nature of the industry; the intensity of project-orientedness in the organization; organizational structure (vertical, horizontal, matrix, centralization); organizational context; and how different units and departments interact with each other (Lusa & Miranda, 2017). Furthermore, project characteristics and nature such as the number of activities and their interdependencies; the number of constrained resources; ambiguity or clarity of the project outcomes; the size of the project; and the project value are critical attributes that impact PMS utilization effectiveness (Vijayasathy & Butler, 2016). There are also several factors attributed to the users that could affect the perceived benefit and the fit between the individual and the PMS, such as the users' tasks and position; level of project management knowledge and skills; and IT self-efficacy (Kumar et al., 2017). Also, the system characteristics such as its reliability; functional capability; ease of use; and flexibility as determinant factors, along with the other socio-techno factors for the holistic view of PMS and user fitness must be considered (Anbari et al., 2008; Belout & Gauvreau, 2004; Fernandez-Aleman et al., 2016). All these factors need to be studied further to construct a reliable and evidence-based model of PMS package usage.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

This paper employed a qualitative study approach, called Echo Method, to investigate the socio-technical perception and the impact of project management software (PMS) in logistic and distribution center in a Saudi Arabian Telecommunication Company. This study provided an in-depth understanding of the socio-technical interaction between PMS and its users. It also determined what possible factors have an impact on articulating the way this relation occurs. After performing the open-ended interviews, this paper's analysis categorized the qualitative data into three categories: positive events, negative events, and coping mechanisms. The examples under each category were further categorized based on theme similarity. This paper has categorized the 204 positive examples into the following themes: Reliability, Ease of Use, Flexibility, Decision Making, Communication & Collaboration, Scheduling & Resource Allocation, and Control. Most of the positive event examples as mentioned by the PMS users interviewed fall under "Control" (30%), followed by Rescheduling and Resource Allocation (25%). Previous works in this field support these results. Included in the discussions are the problems associated with an excessive control in organizations. "Reliability" was the group with the smallest number of positive examples because all features under this category are basic features that are usually not mentioned as long as the users are satisfied with the outcomes.

The 134 adverse element situations have the following six themes/sub-categories: Lack of Ease of Use, Lack of Control, Poor Decision Making, Poor Scheduling and Resource Allocation, Not Flexible, and Unreliability. The most substantial proportion of negative-event examples is in the “Unreliability” category (43%), and the lowest is for the “Lack of Control” category (3.7%), and we have explained the rationale behind these tendencies for the higher and the lower percentage divisions.

The 131 coping mechanism categories have been sub-categorized into the following themes: Workaround, Using Other Tools, Seeking Help, Tolerance, and Recheck and Redoing. The dominant variety handling mechanism is Using Other Tools (41%), while the least dominant category is Rechecking and Redoing (4%). Excel is the most preferred “used another tool” to perform the functions that PMS can't process or processes with poor outcomes.

Lack of employees' involvement in the selection or defining the functionality package needed of the PMS has significant consequences in the misfit between the PMS and its users. The gap between the sought outcomes of the PMS and the realized benefit is a complex interaction among many factors attributed to system characteristics, individual characteristics, organization characteristics, industry maturity with project management, organization context, project characteristics, project value, and project size.

PMS technology providers need to look at the results of these studies carefully and improve their offerings accordingly. For example, this study revealed that PMS users are extensively using Excel to resolve many shortcomings of the existing PMS. Software vendors must look at the lack of functionality or reduced processing of the sought functions. Using Excel's full functionality capability could be one of the quick fixes. Among the other issues, the most important is the perception that PMS is unreliable. PMS developers need to sponsor focused studies to address the sub-categories of reliability issues to tackle them effectively.

Companies need to select the PMS that fits their actual need, not merely following the market trend. They need to seek their employees' feedback for their needs and expectations and to make them active participants during the implementation and commissioning stages to address drawbacks at the right time. Also, companies need to use the planning/scheduling and resource allocation tools throughout the project life-cycle and not only during the initial stage of the project. Furthermore, the organization needs to not use excessive control via PMS or other tools because this could unexpectedly raise the cost of the overall project and deteriorate the company profitability and competitiveness, as autocratic style will not fit with highly innovative organizations and will not fit with the unique nature of most projects nowadays.

Future research on project management software should focus on the identification of specific project management features, its network connectivity as well as its integration with Excel or a similar spreadsheet. In addition to the project management software, the research should focus on what training program on the use of project management software will be most efficient so that the staff would have a full-grasp of the software.

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